

THE IMAGE OF AMIR TIMUR IN UZBEK DRAMATURGY

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Annotation: The article illustrates the history of the origin of the image of Amir **Timur** in fiction, the illumination of the figure of the great ruler in the poetic drama "**Timur the Great**" by an Uzbek poet and statesman Abdulla Oripov, the description of his spiritual and human image, his love and care for ordinary people, his children and grandchildren. At the same time, the poet's skills are analyzed in the example of scenes showing his harshness and justice.

Keywords: person, image, historical, literary, human, religious, event, allegory.

L. Keren, a western researcher, wrote about Amir Timur's state policy and noted that: "Amir Timur showed huge respect towards justice, that's why no person was hurt or oppressed in his reign. He respected both science and the people of science, and his noblest goal was to achieve the prosperity of culture and art throughout his kingdom. There is not enough time to talk about his highness, who had shown many generosities."¹

The personality of Amir Timur, who left a great mark on the life of the Eastern countries, has been the cause of constant debates even though several centuries have passed. It is probably for this reason that various historical and literary works were created about the personality and image of Timur. L. Keren wrote in his "The reign of Amir Timur": "The known works to us by Sharafuddin Ali Yazdi and Ibn Arabshah, one of Voltaire's "An Essay on Universal History, the Manners, and Spirit of Nations" is dedicated to Amir Timur." Italian, Spanish and English dramatists, following the example of Voltaire, created plays. Naturally, their quality was much lower. And

¹ Keren L. Amir Temur saltanati. –Toshkent. Fan nashriyoti, 2018. –B.6.

Vivaldi created an opera that has been completely forgotten today. Goethe mentions Amir Timur a lot in his poems included in "**West-Eastern Diwan**", and in interesting comments, he even states that he intends to write a separate work about Sahibqiran. Jean Auben, who used a number of primary sources rather than the misleading analyzes of his predecessors, created a strong and complex image of Sahibqiron in two articles written on the basis of clear evidence, but we can be sure that **the secrets of Timur's personality and activities have not been revealed.**"²

In poetic drama "**Timur the Great**" by Abdulla Oripov, the character of the passionate Timur was written with great pride. In the drama, the main focus is not on the image of battles and destructive wars, but on the thoughts, opinions, observations, efforts, anger and love of the main character about life and people. It is true, that many works of art have been created about Amir Timur. But Abdulla Oripov did not repeat the content, images, and allusions expressed in these works. Amir Timur's strictness and justice are reflected in the drama, along with his love and care for working people, soldiers, artists, children and grandchildren. A clear proof of this is the conversation between Timur and the barber at the beginning of the drama. Abdulla Oripov painted this scene so skillfully that he was able to paint in fine colors how Amir Timur, sometimes kind, sometimes angry, was a sincere conversationalist, even friendly, from to the holder of a simple position to the holder of the highest position in his kingdom. Maybe that's why the poet describes a great ruler like Timur at the beginning of his drama, not in the circle of the riches, but in an ordinary barber's conversation:

Timur:

*"Har qandayin bandaga ham kerakdir sirdosh
Senga ko'ngil ochsam bo'lar ..."*

Sartarosh:

"Qulluq, Hazratim".³

From these words taken from the speech of Amir Timur's character in the drama, it can be understood that he was able to find friends even among ordinary people.

Literary critic S. Mirzaev commented on the drama "Sahibkiran" in his book "Uzbek Literature of the 20th Century": "Amir Timur never excused those who betrayed the Motherland and the people, and severely punished the sinners. In the drama of Abdulla Oripov, these qualities of Sahibkiran, and his great services to the country and the people are revealed one after another. As a result, the great and noble, lively and natural image of Amir Timur is clearly manifested in the work. He is embodied as a skillful general, a just (fair) king, a ruler who highly appreciates human

² Keren L. Amir Temur saltanati. –Toshkent. Fan nashriyoti, 2018. –B.12.

³ Oripov A. Sahibqiron. Drama. –Toshkent. Yangi nashr, 2019. –B.4.

and religious laws and consistently follows them, a kind father, and a person who has a deep understanding of literature and art and a unique taste", - says that and highly appreciates A. Oripov's work. ⁴

Abdulla Oripov weaves the plot of events so skillfully that it plays an important role in creating the psychological image of Timur, his mental state and revealing his inner world. After the conversation between the barber and Timur, the development of events takes on another level of seriousness, another level of acceleration. In it, the vices of Amir Husayn are vividly revealed, contrasting with the nobility and forgiveness of Timur. It is depicted in the drama that Husayn swears an oath with Kalomullah in the middle, but does not keep his promise. Even in such difficult situations, Timur is forgiving. The drama commemorates the battle against Jete, which took place along the Syrdarya River. In the verses quoted from Timur, Husain is condemned as the person who caused the defeat of the battle:

*"Lashkarini siylamagan sen – xasis amir
Ust-boshi ho'l holdan toygan sening lashkaring
Och-u nahor bo'lgani-chun ortga chekindi".⁵*

Amir Timur says that Husain lacks experience and knowledge in this battle. A. Oripov brings the same content to Timur's speech so skillfully that today it is worth showing it as a historical example and challenge to young people. In this scene, the poet reveals the life of people who are left in the abyss of illiteracy and ignorance:

*"Umringda hech kitob ko'rmay ulg'aygan eding,
Shu sababdan gaplaringda mantiq yo'q, amir", - ⁶ he exclaims.*

The real reason for the defeat in the battle was the discord that arose between the supporters of Timur and Amir Husayn during the battle. However, later, different stories about the defeat in the battle began to spread. About this battle, L. Keren said: "There was a legend about the rain and flood called by a Mongolian sorcerer who owned a stone named Yada. According to one of the properties of this magical stone, its owner can make terrible rain at any time. Warned by this, Ilyaskhoja's army built water-proof fences, and his soldiers dug trenches in their barracks at night. The warriors of Movarounnahr froze to the bone. On top of that, they faced the morning without batting an eye. In the morning they lined up exhausted, cold and angry. Bows that were drawn wet and loose in battle were of no use. This battle, which ended in defeat, went down in history as the "Mud Battle", he wrote.⁷

⁴ Mirzaev S. XX asr o'zbek adabiyoti. –Toshkent. Yangi asr avlodi, 2005. –B.394

⁵ Oripov A. Sohibqiron. Drama. –Toshkent. Yangi nashr, 2019. –B.9.

⁶ Oripov A. Sohibqiron. Drama. –Toshkent. Yangi nashr, 2019. –B.7.

⁷ Keren L. Amir Temur saltanati. –Toshkent. Fan nashriyoti, 2018. –B.24.

In creating the image of Amir Timur, in order to reveal his creativity and familiarity with beauty, A. Oripov paints him not surrounded by battles, but more among the people of art, in the circle of great scientists and scholars. A. Oripov introduces Hafiz Shirozi, the sultan of poetry, to the drama scene. In this conversation, we can feel the familiarity of Amir Timur, who is famous for martial arts and politics and for literature.

Timur:

*“Agar ko ‘nglimni shod etsa o‘sha Sheroz jononi
Qaro xoliga baxsh etgum Samarqand-u Buxoroni.
Shundoqmi?”*

*Samarqand-u Buxoro deb dunyoni oldim, bir xol uchun siz ulari hadiya
etmishsiz. Shunchalikmi?”*

Hofiz:

*“Bisotimni g‘azallarga ulasha berib
Shundoq holga tushib qoldim,
Nochor yupunman,
Oqibatda majbur bo‘lib bitta xol uchun
Dunyodagi eng betakror ikki shaharni
Samarqand-u Buxoroni hadya etganman”.*

Timur (qah-qah urib):

*“Bizning ulug‘ shaharlarni baholash uchun
Bundan ortiq tashbeh bo‘lmas, tasanno sizga”.*⁸

After the annexation of Shiraz to the Sultanate, the most skilled artisans of the city were brought to Samarkand and involved in creative work. According to a small narration, the poet Hafiz also met Sahibqiran at that time. When the great Emir asks him why he dared to give Samarkand-u-Bukhara-to the only birthmark of his beloved in his gazelle, Hafiz pointed to the modest clothes he was wearing and said that he was punished for this foolishness.

In a drama, the image of an event draws the reader’s attention and captivates him. This is Amir Timur’s special respect and love for women. While Bibikhanim and Amir Timur are talking, Mironshah’s wife Khanzodabegim asks for permission to enter and complains that Mironshah raised his hands a lot when he was drunk. Noticing everything from this conversation, Timur called his son him and gave him a lot of advice. He punishes his son by saying that he will spend 40 days in prison for this.

Timur (Mironshohga):

“Ayol zoti xonadonning shamchirog‘idir,

⁸ Oripov A. Sohibqiron. Drama. –Toshkent. Yangi nashr, 2019. –B.56.

O'sha chiroq o'chmasin, deb jang qilamiz-ku!

Endi esa, zindonga bor!

Qirq kun yotgaysan".⁹

Historical sources also contain information about other deeds of the madman Miran Shah. Sultan Ahmed, who took advantage of Miran Shah's nonsense, recaptured Baghdad with the help of Karakoyunli - Turkmens, and the Georgians took advantage of this and began to rebel. Miran Shah destroyed the tombs of famous Muslims, including the tomb of the famous historian Rashiduddin (Rashiduddin - approximately 1247-1318 - an Iranian physician and historian, served as prime minister in the palace of the son of the Mongol khan Haloku Khan. He was the author of the book "Collection of Chronicles" containing the histories of Juhud, Iranian, Arab, Turkish, Mongolian, Indian and Chinese and a number of religious-philosophical treatises written in Arabic), and moved the corpses to the Jewish cemetery.

Hearing this, a number of amirs felt that Amir Timur was getting more and angrier and threw themselves at his feet and asked for mercy for Mironshah, who was concussed as a result of a heavy fall from his horse. However, the fiercer Timur's anger was, the more his love was abundant.

In conclusion, while creating the character of Timur in the poetic drama "Sahibqiron", A. Oripov does not describe him by separating him from the scope of time and space, historical environment and conditions, man and human qualities, but as a person with human qualities, views, his own as a real offspring of the era he lived in, he writes with beautiful lines. In each scene of the drama, the unique poet gives new lines to the image of Timur, enriches it with new allusions and colorful artistic paints.

Reference:

1. Oripov A. Sohibqiron. Drama. –Toshkent. Yangi nashr. 2019.
2. Keren L. Amir Timur saltanati. –Toshkent. Fan nashriyoti. 2018.
3. Mirzaev S. XX asr o'zbek adabiyoti. –Toshkent. Yangi asr avlodi. 2005.

⁹ Oripov A. Sohibqiron. Drama. –Toshkent. Yangi nashr, 2019. –B.38.